

[P-T-602] FV LEIDEN, FII G20210A AND MTHFR T677T GENOTYPES: IS THEIR EVALUATION A USEFUL TOOL IN THE ETIOLOGICAL APPROACH OF THE EARLY RECURRENT PREGNANCY LOSSES IN THE GREEK POPULATION?

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Introduction: Early recurrent pregnancy loss defined as the occurrence of three consecutive first-trimester pregnancy losses, affects 1% of women at the reproductive age. It has been suggested that inherited thrombophilic factors increase the incidence of recurrent pregnancy losses. The data on this topic in the literature are conflicting. The aim of this study was to determine the incidence of the factor V Leiden, FII G20210 and MTHFR C677T mutations, in women who have had an obstetric history of first-trimester recurrent pregnancy losses and negative personal thromboembolic history, in order to evaluate, whether this molecular testing is sine qua non for the rationale approach for this pregnancy complication in the Greek population.

Methods: The study was conducted in 212 women with history of first-trimester recurrent pregnancy losses and 181 women with negative history for pregnancy complications, and at least 2 pregnancies with normal outcome. All the women of the study have had a negative history for thromboembolic disease. Peripheral blood was tested for the factor V Leiden, factor II G20210A and methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase gene C677T mutation.

Results: The frequency of FV Leiden, FII G20210A and MTHFR T677T genotypes was not found increased in women with a history of early recurrent pregnancy loss compared to the control group. The laboratory evaluation for the FV Leiden, FII G20210A and MTHFR C677T mutations in Greek women with this type of pregnancy complication and negative history for thromboembolic disease is unwarranted.

Conclusions: In our population, we conclude that the molecular thrombophilic testing is not indicated for women with early recurrent pregnancy losses, and negative thrombophilic history. Mougou A, Karakantza M, Androutsopoulos G, Decavalas G, Zoumbos N. FV LEIDEN, FII G20210A AND MTHFR T677T GENOTYPES: IS THEIR EVALUATION A USEFUL TOOL IN THE ETIOLOGICAL APPROACH OF THE EARLY RECURRENT PREGNANCY LOSSES IN THE GREEK POPULATION?. *J Thromb Haemost* 2007; 5 Supplement 2: P-T-602

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